

GOALS AND OBJECTIVES OF ENSURING OPENNESS AND TRANSPARENCY IN THE ACTIVITIES OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES

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Abstract: The purpose of ensuring openness and transparency in the activities of internal affairs bodies is to strengthen trust between the state and society, protect the rights and freedoms of citizens, and uphold the rule of law. To achieve this goal, internal affairs bodies must conduct their activities openly and transparently, ensure information accessibility, and enhance public oversight. The tasks include preventing violations, combating corruption, establishing open dialogue with citizens, and facilitating the free flow of information through modern technologies. This abstract examines the importance of transparency in the activities of internal affairs bodies and ways to implement it.

Keywords: Internal affairs bodies, openness, transparency, rule of law, public oversight, anti-corruption, freedom of information, public trust, modern technologies, protection of rights.

The purpose of ensuring the openness and transparency of the activities of internal affairs bodies is the formation of a democratic national system for the effective organization of human rights and freedoms, public order and security, the fight against crime, and its prevention in society by achieving the openness and transparency of the activities of their structural subdivisions, guaranteeing the right of individuals and legal entities to seek, receive, and use information, as well as ensuring the protection of information and the information security of the individual, society, and the state.

To achieve this goal:

- a) creation of conditions and specific mechanisms for the unimpeded search and receipt by individuals and legal entities of information on the activities of all structural subdivisions of internal affairs bodies;
- b) development of mechanisms ensuring legal access to information on the activities of internal affairs bodies;
- c) accurate and flawless functioning of mechanisms for disseminating information on the activities of internal affairs bodies in compliance with the requirements of the law;
- d) the availability of the necessary professional knowledge, skills, and experience of persons responsible for ensuring the openness of the activities of internal affairs bodies;
- d) full compliance with the basic principles of openness of the activities of structural subdivisions of internal affairs bodies;
- e) ensuring the inevitability of responsibility for non-compliance with the requirements for ensuring the openness of the activities of internal affairs bodies, non-compliance with or violation of regulations.

The multifaceted nature of the activities carried out by internal affairs bodies, the close connection with the fulfillment of such complex tasks as the protection of state and official

secrets, as well as the protection of human rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests, ensuring public order and public safety, combating crime, and preventing offenses, as well as the constant presence in society of malicious destructive forces opposing their activities, determine the complexity and high responsibility of ensuring the openness of certain processes and stages of the activities of internal affairs bodies. Therefore, every employee is required, first of all, to know the basic principles of openness of the activities of internal affairs bodies and their essence, as well as to strictly adhere to them.

According to Article 4 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Openness of the Activities of State Authorities and Administration," the main principles of openness of the activities of internal affairs bodies are:

- accessibility, timeliness and reliability of the information provided by them;
- openness and transparency of their activities;
- freedom to seek, receive, and disseminate information about the activities of internal affairs bodies;
- observance of the rights and legitimate interests of citizens to protect their honor and dignity from encroachments, interference in their private life, as well as the rights of citizens and legal entities to protect their business reputation when providing information about the activities of internal affairs bodies.

Information provided by the responsible body or official, defined by the current regulatory legal acts on the activities of all sectoral services of internal affairs bodies and their structural subdivisions, is accessible to everyone, that is, any restrictions are not allowed, taking into account the social status of the user or other circumstances. In addition, information on the activities of internal affairs bodies must be provided in a timely manner, within the time limits established by current legislation. In any case, the information provided regarding the activities of internal affairs bodies must be reliable, that is, based on accurate facts and information, and verified in advance.

Openness and transparency of the activities of internal affairs bodies, that is, the sectoral service and its structural subdivisions must carry out their activities openly, in the presence of others and without concealment from them. For example, a prevention inspector or a responsible employee of the road safety service is required to draw up a report and other documents on the identified administrative offense in the presence of the person who committed the offense, witnesses, with an open explanation of their rights. In accordance with part 4 of Article 88 of the Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the investigator, inquiry officer, prosecutor, judge are obliged to take measures not to disclose information about the private life of the suspect, accused, defendant, victim, and others identified during the investigation and trial. For this, the circle of persons participating in investigative or judicial actions, in which such information can be revealed, is limited, and the participants are warned about liability for their disclosure[1].

Internal affairs bodies and their officials cannot provide information constituting state secrets or other secrets protected by law. Legislation on the rights and freedoms of citizens, the procedure for their implementation, as well as legislation establishing the legal status of sectoral services and their structural subdivisions, and open funds of information systems of internal affairs bodies are not classified as confidential information. Internal affairs bodies are obliged to inform the mass media about events, facts, incidents, and processes affecting the interests of society in the manner prescribed by law.

Information on the activities of internal affairs bodies must be freely accessible to all legal entities and individuals, and its accuracy and reliability must be ensured. Any misinterpretation and falsification of information related to the activities of internal affairs bodies is prohibited and entails liability. Those who disseminate information concerning the activities of internal affairs bodies are liable for the accuracy of the information, together with the person who provided this information and the author who published it, in the manner prescribed by law.

The state protects the right of individuals and legal entities to seek, receive, verify, disseminate, use, and store information related to the activities of internal affairs bodies. Restriction of the right to receive information on the activities of internal affairs bodies based on sex, race, nationality, language, religion, social origin, convictions, personal and social status is not permitted.

Internal affairs bodies and their officials are obliged, in the manner prescribed by law, to provide individuals and legal entities with the opportunity to familiarize themselves with information affecting their rights, freedoms, and legitimate interests, to create accessible information resources, and to provide users with information on their rights, freedoms, and obligations, their security, and other issues affecting the interests of society.

In addition, when providing information on the activities of internal affairs bodies, it is required to observe the rights and legitimate interests of citizens to protect their honor and dignity from encroachments, interference in their private life, as well as the rights of citizens and legal entities to protect their business reputation.

According to Article 29 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, individuals and legal entities have the right to seek, receive, and disseminate information of their choice, with the exception of information directed against the current constitutional order and other restrictions established by law. There is also limited access to information about the activities of internal affairs bodies to protect human rights and freedoms, legitimate interests, maintain public order and ensure public safety, combat crime, and prevent offenses within the limits of their powers established by current legislation.

Access to information on the activities of internal affairs bodies is restricted if this information is classified as state secrets or other secrets protected by law in the manner prescribed by law. The list of information relating to restricted access information on the activities of internal affairs bodies, as well as the procedure for classifying information as such, are determined by the legislation of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan and departmental regulatory legal acts adopted on its basis.

The user of information on the activities of internal affairs bodies is a natural or legal person carrying out the search for this information. According to Article 7 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Openness of the Activities of State Authorities and Administration" [3], a user of information on the activities of internal affairs bodies has the right:

- receiving and disseminating reliable information about the activities of internal affairs bodies;
- to apply with a request for information on the activities of internal affairs bodies, not limited by law, directly or through their representatives;
- refusal to receive information about the activities of internal affairs bodies.

A user of information on the activities of internal affairs bodies may have other rights in accordance with the legislation.

Heads of internal affairs bodies in the sphere of ensuring the openness of the activities of internal affairs bodies have the following powers:

- coordination of the activities of structural and territorial subdivisions of internal affairs bodies to ensure access to information about their activities by users;
- organization of the development and adoption of regulatory legal acts, normative and other documents defining the procedure for providing information on the activities of internal affairs bodies;
- organization of monitoring and constant comprehensive assessment of the activities carried out to ensure the openness of the activities of internal affairs bodies;
- determination of officials responsible for providing information on the activities of internal affairs bodies;
- approval of the list of information on the activities of internal affairs bodies, posted on their official websites;
- approval of a list of information on the activities of internal affairs bodies, the access to which is restricted in accordance with the legislation;
- approval of information materials on the activities of internal affairs bodies subject to publication;
- establishing the procedure for the presence of information users at open collegial meetings of internal affairs bodies;
- ensuring unimpeded access of information users to information on the activities of internal affairs bodies, with the exception of information, access to which is restricted by law;
- ensuring the timeliness and reliability of information on the activities of internal affairs bodies, posted on their official websites;
- taking appropriate measures against officials of state authorities and administration for violation of legislation on the openness of the activities of internal affairs bodies.

Heads of internal affairs bodies may also exercise other powers in the field of ensuring the openness of the activities of internal affairs bodies in accordance with the legislation.

Today, the press services of the internal affairs bodies are an integral part of the relevant internal affairs body in which they are created. Ensuring the openness of the activities of internal affairs bodies, based on the requirements of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Openness of the Activities of State Authorities and Administration," requires amendments and additions to the regulatory legal acts of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its structural subdivisions related to this activity.

References:

1. Collection of Legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2014, No. 19, Art. 209; 2017, No. 37, Art. 978; National Database of Legislation, August 30, 2019, No. 03/19/559/3670; National Database of Legislation, April 21, 2021, No. 03/21/683/0375.
2. Criminal Procedure Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - T., 2014. - P. 54.
3. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Operational-Investigative Activities" of December 25, 2012 // Bulletin of the Chambers of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan. - 2012. - No12. - P. 335.

